

The Electrical Conductivity of Potassium Chloride in Certain Mixed Solvents.

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The object of this work was to discover whether non-electrolyte molecules possess dipole moments group themselves round the ions of an electrolyte in a solution which contains both. If any such groups are formed, the mobility of the ion will be changed. If an unsolvated ion becomes the centre of such a group, its mobility should become smaller; but a solvated ion might have its group of solvent molecules replaced by a smaller group of molecules of non-electrolyte, in which case the mobility would increase.

The substances chosen were potassium chloride as the electrolyte, and as non-electrolytes, methyl, ethyl and isopropyl alcohols and acetone. All these have reasonably high dipole moments and are miscible with water in all proportions. The electrical conductivity of potassium chloride in a mixture of water and each of these non-electrolytes was determined over a considerable range of concentrations, and an attempt was made to interpret the results.

The potassium chloride and acetone used were analytical reagents, and the alcohols had been purified by distillation over quicklime twice. Water for the conductivity determinations was prepared in a Hartley's still, the first and last thirds being rejected. It had a specific conductivity of 2×10^{-6} ohms⁻¹. The usual precautions were observed in storing and using all these substances. The cell was an old one of hard glass, with electrodes of bright platinum foil. (Platinized electrodes promote the atmospheric oxidation of alcohols: Partington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1937). The resistance was determined by means of a Pye bridge and buzzer. Temperature control was by means of a thermostat kept constant at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.1$.

Each solution was made up as follows: the required quantities of non-electrolyte and of a known concentrated solution of potassium chloride were mixed, made up to 50 c. c. by addition of water, and

transferred to the cell, which was then allowed to remain in the thermostat for twenty minutes to attain the right temperature. The resistance was then determined. When solutions in 100% non-electrolyte were possible, these were prepared separately. Viscosities were measured with a pycnometer and Ostwald viscometer. It was found that the effect of potassium chloride was negligible when compared with that of the non-electrolytes; and viscosity-composition curves for the liquid mixtures employed were determined. The viscosity of pure water was taken to be 8.95×10^{-3} at 25° .

The results in the case of water-ethyl alcohol mixtures are in good general agreement with those of Walker and Hambly (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 61), whose electrolyte was diethylamine hydrochloride. This type of behaviour is well known. Complex relations in the case of water-acetone mixtures have previously been observed by Jones and Mahin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 41, 433;) *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 69, 389) and other workers. Solutions of potassium chloride in these mixtures do not appear to have been investigated, nor have irregularities similar to those discussed in this paper been observed. The relevant literature is extensive, but little work on conductivity in mixed solvents has been published in recent years. Modern knowledge of dipole moments and molecular configurations should throw much light on the results of older researches.

TABLE I.

Viscosities and specific conductivities of the liquid mixtures.

% non-electrolyte	0	20	40	60	80	100
Viscosity $\times 10^3$						
Water-MeOH	8.95	12.79	15.43	14.54	11.04	5.99
Water-EtOH	8.95	15.24	21.94	22.46	18.65	12.08
Water-acetone	8.95	12.04	13.36	12.64	7.29	3.49
Sp. conducy. $\times 10^6$						
Water-MeOH			2.8	3.8	5.0	7.6
Water-acetone		5.66	4.04			

Where the specific conductivity is not given, it is less than 2.8×10^{-6} , the limit set by our bridge. In the case of water-EtOH and water-PrOH mixtures, it is always less than this value. Percentage of non-electrolyte is expressed by volume.

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TABLE II.

Equivalent conductivity of KCl in aqueous alcohol.

% of alcohol	0	20	40	60	80	90	100
	Water—MeOH						
<i>N</i> /10-KCl	128.9	94.8	73.2	64.4	60.8	59.6	
<i>N</i> /20	133.0	93.9	73.6	64.0	61.6		
<i>N</i> /50	138.4	96.9	75.3	66.6	65.9		75.4
<i>N</i> /100	141.2	102.3	81.2	70.4	72.0		80.7
<i>N</i> /500	146.3	104.6	81.3	74.6	76.5		95.1
<i>N</i> /1000	147.4	105.7	82.4	76.0	79.4		100.2
	Water—EtOH						
<i>N</i> /10	128.9	78.0	53.0	38.0	26.5		
<i>N</i> /20	133.0	81.0	54.3	40.3	29.9		
<i>N</i> /50	138.4	86.5	57.1	43.0	33.2	29.5	
<i>N</i> /100	141.2	89.1	59.1	45.2	37.1	33.7	
<i>N</i> /500	146.3	92.4	61.7	49.7	42.2	39.6	
<i>N</i> /1000	147.4	93.6	64.3	52.4	44.9	41.0	
	Water—isoPrOH						
<i>N</i> /10	128.9	78.5	48.8	29.5	17.0		
<i>N</i> /1000	147.4	85.3	54.0	35.8	25.9		

TABLE III.

Equivalent conductivity of KCl in aqueous acetone.

% of acetone	0	0.1	1	5	10	20	30	40	60	80	90
<i>N</i> /5-KCl	123.9	123.9	123.9	115.0	107.4	92.0	80.5	70.0	53.7		
<i>N</i> /7	127.0	132.5	132.5	125.1	115.5	102.4	86.6	77.6	59.2		
<i>N</i> /10	128.9	133.7	133.7	125.8	116.7	103.5	86.7	78.3	60.6	40.1	
<i>N</i> /20	133.0	133.0	131.5	123.2	111.6	97.0	85.7	76.9	61.7	40.6	
<i>N</i> /50	138.4	139.7	137.1	129.6	118.0	103.6	90.7	81.5	67.6	57.0	
<i>N</i> /100	141.2	141.2	137.8	130.1	120.2	106.8	91.6	83.7	71.5	63.6	61.6
<i>N</i> /500	146.3	141.9	140.5	132.9	125.3	108.8	94.9	86.8	77.6	77.2	84.6
<i>N</i> /1000	147.4	146.6	145.9	137.6	129.7	110.6	100.3	89.0	78.9	61.2	94.1

Also, for *N*/2-KCl in 1% acetone, an approximate value of 115 was obtained.

If the equivalent conductivity is plotted against the percentage of each non-electrolyte, families of curves are obtained (one curve for each concentration of potassium chloride). In every case these curves start roughly parallel and sloping steeply downwards, but as the concentration of non-electrolyte increases they slope less and tend to diverge, this effect being greatest in water-acetone, and least in water-*iso*PrOH mixtures. Minima appear in some of the water-acetone and water-MeOH curves, but they never correspond to the maximum viscosity. Irregularities also occur, while the water-EtOH and water-*iso*PrOH curves are smooth and regular. The authors are convinced, from a study of all the curves, that the variation in conductivity cannot be explained wholly, or even primarily, in terms of viscosity, as some workers have attempted to do.

FIG. 1.

Conductivity in aqueous acetone.

Now if the equivalent conductivity is plotted against the square root of the concentration of potassium chloride, other families of curves result (one curve for each non-electrolyte percentage). With pure water and water-EtOH mixtures these approximate to straight lines, indicating complete dissociation on the Debye-Hückel theory. Water-MeOH and water-acetone curves, on the other hand, show a series of regularly spaced maxima and minima (see Fig. 1). The irregularities in the other type of curve, mentioned above, are connected with these. At the higher non-electrolyte concentrations these tend to smooth out, and the curves approximately obey Rudolphi's modification of Ostwald's equation, characteristic of incomplete ionisation.

DISCUSSION.

Although no obvious connection exists between conductivity and viscosity, a relation is apparent between conductivity and the dipole moments of the non-electrolytes employed. The following figures are taken from Glasstone ("Recent Advances in Physical Chemistry," Chap. III).

TABLE IV.

Liquid	MeOH	<i>iso</i> -PrOH	EtOH	Water	Acetone
Dipole moment $\times 10^{18}$	1.64	1.70	1.72	1.60	2.71

It will be observed that those liquids, which have dipole moments near to that of water, give, when mixed with water, the most regular conductivity results, *e.g.*, EtOH and *iso*PrOH. MeOH shows a certain amount of irregularity, while acetone, whose dipole moment is very different from that of water, gives very irregular results.

From Fig. 1, it will be seen that maxima and minima occur on all but the last two curves, and always at the same concentrations of potassium chloride. The concentration of acetone appears to have no effect on their position, although some acetone must be present if they are to occur at all (0.1 % is sufficient), and too much acetone suppresses them. It is possible to calculate the average distance apart of the potassium and chloride ions in solutions exhibiting maxima and minima, taking $N = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$; these distances are given in Table V, which also shows the average relative motions of two ions of opposite sign, calculated from potential gradients actually observed in our cell and the known mobilities of the ions.

TABLE V.

	KCl conc.	Av. distance apart of the ions.	Av. relative motion of the ions.
Minimum	0.4 N	12.9 Å.U.	...
Maximum	0.1156	19.26	70 Å.U.
Minimum	0.0500	25.21	140
Maximum	0.0144	38.56	280
Minimum	0.0064	50.52	360

It will be observed that the distances apart of the ions in the three solutions giving minima, are in the simple ratio of 1:2:4. In the case of the maxima, we get the ratio 1:2. The relation is exact except in the first minimum, which corresponds to an experimental result in $N/2$ solution of doubtful accuracy.

The explanation that immediately suggested itself to us was that of the formation of chains of acetone molecules between the ions, due to the alignment of acetone molecules under the influence of their dipole moments. These chains we called "dipole-association" chains; they would terminate on ions of opposite sign, and would presumably be formed most easily if the average distance between the ions, when moving freely, is equal to the length of a chain composed of an integral number of acetone molecules. They would be broken during the conductivity determinations, unless they were able to withstand the potential gradients employed, since the relative motion of the two ions at the ends of a chain is likely to be much more than twice the length of the chain (compare the figures in the last two columns of Table V).

In order to test this theory, it is necessary to know the molecular dimensions of acetone. The only measurement so far available is that of Hengstenberg and Bru (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1932, 30, 341) who found the C-C distance to be 1.57 ± 4 Å.U. This was combined with the results given for formaldehyde and other simple molecules (*Annual Rep.*, 1932, 29, 63-70) and, as in that paper, allowance was made for a "surface of influence" 0.6 Å.U. thick all round the molecules. The ionic dimensions are those obtained by use of Stokes' law (*cf.* Taylor, "Physical Chemistry," Vol. I, p. 689) and so include this surface of influence. On trial, it was found that the distances apart of ions which are separated by chains of *hydrated* acetone molecules agree quite well with the average distances apart

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of the ions given in Table V, as a comparison of the figures in Table VI with those in Table V will show.

TABLE VI.

No. of acetone mol. in the chain	1	2	3	4	5	6
Distance apart of the terminal ions	11.5	19.0	26.5	34.0	41.5	49.0 Å.U.

It will be seen that there is quite good agreement, except that the one value 38.56 in Table V is replaced by two values 34.0 and 41.5, in Table VI. It is also necessary to explain why some of these values correspond to maxima, and some to minima in the conductivity.

It is very tempting, and not at all difficult to put forward a theory in which these difficulties are explained away by means of one or two subsidiary assumptions. But there is little experimental evidence for such assumptions as yet, and authors wish first of all to extend their investigations in this field.

In conclusion, they desire to express their gratitude to Professors B. L. Vaish and H. Krall for advice and assistance freely given.

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Received June 25, 1935.